

Report on demonstration trials of biopolyesters

Deliverable 4.4

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Lead Partner: NOVAMONT

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The current report represents the deliverable D4.4 "Report on demonstration trials of biopolyesters" within the framework of the SCALIBUR project.

The results herein reported refer to innovative formulations specifically designed for the project's targeted applications. This report on demonstration trials of biopolyesters discusses in detail the properties of developed materials which have been selected, accordingly to the data generated within the reference period, as the final formulations for trays and films for food packaging applications and for organic waste bag applications.

The analysis of the results obtained indicate that it is possible to obtain innovative bio-based materials from OFMSW derived sugars produced by optimised enzymatic hydrolysis, however the yield of the process is dependent on the quality of the waste used for hydrolysis.

The monomer 1,4 bio-BDO is the key building block which has been validated for the optimization tests aimed at formulating and upscaling innovative biomaterials and films for the final applications based on results previously obtained and discussed within D4.2 and 4.3. We demonstrated that targeted optimization trials allow to produce biomaterials with enhanced performances either for food and non-food packaging films.

Moreover, this report provides an overview of the process accordingly to the optimised procedure at Novamont and ITENE's facilities

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